

THE CONTRIBUTION OF CATTLE BREEDING TO THE EXPRESSION OF THE MOUNTAIN AGRO-TOURISM POTENTIAL IN THE CHARPATIAN MOUNTAINS AND DISADVANTAGED RURAL AREAS

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Abstract

The natural area of the Carpathian Mountains in Romania encompasses a set of mountainous agricultural zones where specific geoclimatic conditions and the biodiversity of natural meadows significantly influence the development of animal husbandry and the future of native breeds. As well-known, these factors have a positive impact on the quality and health of products while simultaneously imposing constraints on the productivity of households and micro-farms in mountainous regions. In such conditions, supporting traditional animal husbandry remains the primary occupation of inhabitants in mountainous areas. The aim of this bibliographic work can be summarized as the synthesis and analysis of data with particular relevance in assessing the advantages and disadvantages of animal husbandry in mountainous areas, as well as the factors with a major impact on their socio-economic and touristic development. Small farms between 2–6–10 dairy cows have been analyzed from an economic point of view, resulting in the fact that the higher the number of dairy cows, the greater the farmer's benefits. This study relied on accessing data and information available on Google Scholar and other reputable sources in the field, analyzing them to enrich current knowledge. The paper synthesizes and critically analyzes the advantages and disadvantages of animal husbandry activities in mountainous areas. The invaluable values generated over time by the evolution of the Carpathian mountain potential are detailed, examining their contribution historically, culturally, socially, and economically to the evolution of mountain civilization and the continuous need for efforts to support them.

Keywords: Carpathian areas; mountain households; native breeds; biodiversity.

INTRODUCTION

The Carpathian Mountains of Romania host heterogeneous areas, many of which are distinguished by exceptional biodiversity and agro-touristic potential. Overall, their economic resources are quantitatively and qualitatively more limited than those in submontane and plain rural areas, influenced by much greater distances between localities and socio-economic objectives. These areas share common aspects, derived from similar historical, cultural, and socio-economic development conditions, as well as cultural identity and organization of social communities. In Carpathian mountain regions of particular importance for animal husbandry, the rural economy has primarily relied on traditional animal husbandry in peasant households or microfarms (Sturaro et al., 2013). However, in recent decades, numerous social, economic, technical, and cultural changes have occurred, with correlated effects leading

to the limitation or even abandonment of traditional agriculture (MacDonald et al., 2000; Strijker, 2005). The number of traditional households is continuously decreasing due to abandonment and, especially, their conversion into intensive farms. All these changes have resulted in the reduction of open areas and the multiplication of forested ones (Cocca et al., 2012), alterations that have significantly impacted biodiversity (Giupponi et al., 2006; Marini et al., 2012; Bernués et al., 2005). In Carpathian mountain areas, dairy cattle farming predominates in traditional households and microfarms, providing multifunctional services. The predominant dairy products in these areas are traditional cheeses, known for providing satisfactory added value and, consequently, a decent income for farmers (Bovolenta et al., 2011). The main source of food for animals in these areas is primarily represented by mountain pastures, shaping authentic landscapes and contributing to biodiversity conservation, thus preventing reforestation (Cocca et al., 2012; Giupponi et al., 2006). Such services enhance the tourist vocation of mountainous areas, contributing to the economic and social development of rural communities (Sturaro et al., 2013). For these reasons, maintaining profitable farms that have adapted to environmental constraints and are capable of guaranteeing the conservation of traditional land uses is one of the key issues for rural development in mountainous areas (Bernués et al., 2011). Due to rapid economic development, mechanization, and the allure of migrating to cities, these areas have experienced depopulation to some extent in recent decades. From an economic perspective, commercial units in the mountainous region are classified as disadvantaged areas. These disadvantaged zones mainly include mountain and alpine areas with a humid climate, sometimes hard-to-reach meadows, arid surfaces, or often marshy depressions. Approximately 50% of Romania's total land area falls into this category (MADR, 2015). In these disadvantaged areas, the main activities generating employment are animal husbandry, obtaining cellulosic fodder, exploitation and processing of wood, and tourism. In this context, the primary occupation of locals in these areas is animal husbandry, representing the most important agricultural sector in mountainous regions. Traditional animal husbandry, known since ancient times, has played an essential role in maintaining landscapes and habitats, which, although highly valuable for all rural inhabitants, are increasingly threatened by agricultural intensification (madr.ro., 2015). As is well-known, ruminant herbivores efficiently utilize these meadows and natural habitats, placing them at the forefront of mountain economy (Bonsembiante and Cozzi, 2003). Currently, successful zoeconomic programs are those that ensure the essential prerequisites for supporting the competitiveness of households and farmers (Van der Werf, 1997).

Positive environmental management of these disadvantaged areas, together with achieving adequate income for farmers, renders animal husbandry systems compatible with future increases in the number of livestock breeders and traditional product producers, promoting the expansion of organic food trade. Implementing this agricultural policy adds value to the marketed products by distributing them directly to agrotourism pensions or specialized stores with traditional products, providing communities with a new stage towards sustainable rural development.

ACCESSING DATA AND CONDUCTING THE STUDY PROCEDURE

In order to conduct this monographic study, I consulted a variety of bibliographic sources, including recent and older scientific publications dedicated to the addressed field. Concurrently, I accessed online scientific documentation platforms of high relevance, such as

Google Scholar/Academic and Web of Science, utilizing the following search terms: "mountain area," „native breeds” „agrotourism,” „dairy cow farming in mountainous regions”. The synthesized data was processed descriptively, analyzed comparatively, and subsequently compiled and organized into the following chapters.

NATURAL CONSTRAINTS AFFECTING DISADVANTAGED AREAS

Some agricultural production regions face constraints that impact both the ecological and economic performance of agricultural systems (Marton et al 2016). Farms in mountainous areas typically have limited capacity due to environmental and climatic constraints that restrict options for animal housing and forage production. In such cases, smaller and more costly productions are usually achieved compared to lowland farms, affecting the economic competitiveness of mountainous agricultural systems and potentially threatening their existence (Battaglini et al 2014). Currently, the overall disadvantaged areas in our country encompass 658 localities, spread across approximately 2,089,399 hectares of mountainous agricultural land (MADR, 2023). Disadvantaged mountainous areas exhibit significant diversity in terms of species (cattle, buffalo, sheep, goats, horses) and breeds of animals raised, as well as the products and by-products obtained and marketed. In accordance with these considerations, the following three characteristics are considered relevant in evaluating the raising systems of different species and native breeds of animals (Bibliography):

- Exploitation of pastures for providing the majority of animal feed.
- Exploitation of pasture production under the influence of relief and season.
- Influence of the quantitative and qualitative value of pastures on the nutritional content of animal feed.

CONSTRAINTS RELATED TO PLANT PRODUCTION

Temperature: Below 5°C, vegetation growth in general, and grasses in particular, is negligible. However, if the temperature becomes oscillating and rises above 6°C, it becomes optimal for vegetation. Altitude also significantly influences ambient temperature. For example, at altitudes of 140–700 m, with an increase of 30 m in altitude, pasture production decreases by 2% (MADR, 2023). Nevertheless, the productivity effect depends heavily on the season. Significant changes can occur during the plant vegetation period. In spring, higher temperatures allow plants to grow faster by 1–2 weeks, which has a positive impact on animal yields.

Precipitation: Essential for grass growth in mountain pastures, the level of precipitation is crucial. Lack of summer precipitation, coupled with high temperatures, intensifies evaporation and transpiration, leading to the onset of summer droughts with repercussions on the growth of grass cover.

Soil: It encompasses a set of important factors influencing the composition and floristic structure, such as nutrient-rich content (some essential for plant growth), pH, water retention capacity, permeability, soil texture, and structure. All these factors play a crucial role in achieving performance in livestock farming in mountainous areas (MADR, 2023).

Animal Nutrition: The most important factor for productive performance. When aiming for increased milk production or carcass weight, feed rations must be well-balanced both

quantitatively and qualitatively to support physiological processes, lactation, reproduction, and ultimately, health.

Reproductive indices: In ruminants and other animal species, these parameters are largely influenced by the level of feed ration and its quality. As well-known, feed ration level significantly optimizes reproductive performance by increasing ovulation rates and reducing embryonic abortions.

Milk Production: Ensures the growth and health of newborns and sucklings, as well as human consumption at the household and/or community level. However, the achievement of milk production largely depends on the genotype of each animal. Females with a higher genetic potential for increased milk production are more predisposed to enhance and mobilize body reserves to support a better and longer lactation (Sturaro et al., 2013).

Growth and development: Any nutritional disturbance in young animals, usually caused by restricting milk consumption in calves for a quicker transition to conventional feeding, or in adults due to a decrease in the quantity and quality of feed, will have severe repercussions on growth rate.

CARACTERISTICS OF ANIMAL PRODUCTION SYSTEM IN DISADVANTAGED MOUNTAIN AREAS

In general, almost all animal production systems in mountainous areas are linked to an extensive system of raising species and breeds of animals. Although intensive systems of raising pigs and poultry are predominant, there are still households and small farms where these species are raised in traditional ecological systems (Sturaro et al., 2013). Here are some characteristics and advantages of traditional ecological systems found in the Carpathian mountain areas.

Breed and genotype have a less productive potential in the case of native breeds, which, however, are much more resistant and better adapted to the harsh environmental conditions specific to mountain and alpine areas. Attempts to exploit modern animal breeds in mountainous areas, even under appropriate management, have not yielded results, as these breeds cannot adapt to the climate, altitude, and diet conditions as effectively as native breeds, historically adapted to these conditions.

Small ruminants (sheep and goats) possess natural morpho-physiological adaptations, such as thin and mobile lips and tongues, which facilitate the selection and consumption of specific mountainous grasses. This enables them to effectively utilize a wide range of forage sources. Pastures with low-quality grass cover are well-utilized by these species, which have the ability to select plants with higher digestibility. It is crucial to note that small ruminants tend to choose plants with a higher digestibility compared to larger ruminants, resulting in a greater volume of digestible organic matter and a higher intake of metabolizable energy.

Environmental conditions reflect the approach used in selecting species and breeds of animals suitable for the respective area. It should be noted that the choice of a production system can, through various management methods, alter the environment or feeding system. The use of directed and controlled grazing, with the application of organic fertilizers, can lead to the improvement of pasture composition over time. In mountainous and alpine

areas, the potential to achieve high levels of biological performance within animal husbandry systems is lower compared to submontane, hilly, or plain areas. This is largely due to the seasonal nature of plant production in mountainous regions, which imposes significant nutritional limitations on animal husbandry systems.

The advantages of raising cattle must be correlated with the constraints in disadvantaged mountainous areas, which sometimes limit the processing activities of animal products, concurrently restricting income growth and job opportunities. The global population explosion necessitates an increased rate of food production, primarily through the growth of cattle, species that significantly contribute to ensuring food security. This becomes a crucial instrument that should be implemented in the economic and social policies of each country.

We consider one of the most important branches in global agriculture to be the raising of cattle, a species with a good capacity for adaptation to mountainous conditions. Current statistics show that cattle provide approximately 95% of the total amount of milk consumed worldwide, 30–35% of the total amount of meat, and around 90–92% of the total processed hides in various industries (Sturaro et al., 2013).

Despite a cow being able to provide, under normal growth conditions, the milk needs for 10–15 people and the meat needs for 6–8 people, according to FAO statistics (2023), over a billion people suffer from malnutrition, with approximately 20–25% being children under 5 years old.

It is considered that from the physiological protein requirement for an adult, which is approximately 0.57 g/kg body weight/day, milk and beef from cattle should constitute about 50%, surpassing those of plant origin, at least from an energetic standpoint (Dascălu, 2007). According to FAO statistics (2023), it is assumed that an animal obtains a calorie of energy through the consumption of about 5–6 calories of plant energy.

From the consulted data, it is evident that cattle (taurines) continue to represent the most important and numerous animal species globally, efficiently exploiting plant fodder and contributing significantly to the protection of natural landscapes and sustainable management of rural areas (Maciuc, Leonte, Radu-Rusu, 2015). In animal husbandry science, the concept of sustainability encompasses multiple dimensions, including environmental protection, animal welfare, biodiversity, food safety and quality, social issues, and economic competitiveness (Gamborg and Sandøe, 2005).

The exceptional capacity of cattle to utilize plant fodder and transform it into basic products for human consumption places them at the forefront of animal production systems in our country (<https://www.studentie.ro/universitar/referate/fiziologia-digestiei-la-rumegatoare>). The high level of sophistication in specialized family microfarms demonstrates the effectiveness of this system practiced in many countries with advanced agriculture and remarkable zoeconomic results, ensured by milk and meat productions.

In households and family microfarms specializing in dairy cattle, the majority of tasks are carried out by family members, with occasional hiring of external laborers during the summer season. In countries with high-performance animal husbandry, there are well-technologized mountain farms with automation and cyberization. Under these conditions, large farms (100 beef or even dairy cows) can be fully managed by a single farmer along with their family (Oțiman, 2006).

In the context of adapting to the conditions of animal husbandry specific to our country, the European Union recommends that Romania align the products and by-products from

milk and meat obtained in cattle farming systems with international zootechnical standards. Scientific research, in collaboration with specialists in this field, must provide alternatives for improving subsistence farms, which in the private sector are primarily focused on dairy cattle farming. Law number 18/1991, complemented by law 69/2000 on land ownership, allows for the mobilization of private ownership over agricultural land and animal husbandry, leading to significant changes in this sector. Animal farming in private systems in non-cooperativized areas of mountainous regions operated even before 1989, but lacked financial sources and specific facilities for family mountain microfarms.

In the Carpathian mountain area, households with 1–3 cows predominate, followed by those with 5–6 cows, and to a lesser extent, microfarms with approximately 10 lactating cows. These operations primarily cater to family consumption, and a portion of the milk quantity is sold as it is or in the form of dairy products. The combination of animal farming with agrotourism enhances the economic status of households and farms, as well as the living standards of rural mountainous communities. Family microfarms focused on raising cattle for milk or meat can be considered an essential pillar from a social, economic, and touristic perspective, acting as a fundamental unit in the mountainous rural space. The new concept of technologizing dairy cattle farms supports the expansion of this sector to meet the increased demand for feeding the continuously growing human population, ensuring optimal conditions for achieving economic efficiency (Ujica, Maciuc, Dascălu, 2007).

CHARACTERIZATION OF LOCAL (NATIVE) BREEDS IN THE CARPATIHIAN MONTAIN REGIONS

The local breeds in the mountainous regions of our country can be considered "cultural entities" when analyzed historically, emphasizing that these breeds have often played an essential role in agricultural activities as well as in the social life of communities in these areas (Gandini and Giacomelli, 1997). Additionally, local breeds can be likened to socio-cultural properties as they contribute to preserving ancient local traditions and continuing them without significant modification due to the progress in agriculture (Gandini and Villa, 2003). To assess the historical value of a local breed, a methodology based on a set of parameters can be employed, including antiquity, role in the agricultural system, agricultural techniques, role in the landscape, folklore, crafts, and gastronomy (Gandini and Villa, 2003).

In recent decades, the expansion of intensive animal farming in the context of global economic development has drastically reduced the number of indigenous breeds and populations raised in traditional systems (Ovaska et al., 2021). It is estimated that approximately 30% of local breeds worldwide are at risk of extinction (FAO). Awareness of this reality has prioritized genetic conservation efforts for indigenous breeds, focusing on centers with significant populations to perpetuate these socio-economic and cultural heritages (Mendelsohn, 2003). Their genetic and cultural values are widely recognized by the scientific community, farmers who still maintain them, and the general public (Gandini and Villa, 2003; Ovaska and Soini, 2016; Leroy et al., 2017). The history of indigenous breeds is an important parameter for their cultural value, which often surpasses their genetic value. These breeds are symbolically and materially connected to agrotourism, biodiversity, culture, and traditions (Ovaska et al., 2021). The most important features specific to agrotourism, distinguishing it

from other forms of tourism, are elements generated by primary agricultural and tourist activities.

Among these, a major aspect is the adoption of the farm's lifestyle, the opportunity to interact with animals, traditional fresh foods, the scents of local gastronomy, sounds, getting to know farmers and villagers, and their customs. Noteworthy is also the access to hospitality, new knowledge and friendships, the tradition and history of villages in mountainous regions, culture and customs, folklore, authentic space, the natural environment, freedom of movement, peace, and recreational opportunities, etc. (Jęczmyk, Uglis, and Steppa, 2021).

INCOME ESTIMATION WITHIN FARMS IN THE MOUNTAINOUS REGION OF ROMANIA

Although mountain agriculture can take on various forms as diverse as the mountain landscapes themselves, it remains largely a family-based agriculture. These mountain agricultural activities have traditionally sustained individual households, although today they are increasingly expanding into global markets. Nevertheless, mountain farmers tend to be guided by family, cultural, and ecological values rather than profit maximization. The present estimation aims to evaluate the long-term technical and economic efficiency of small dairy farms located in the mountainous region, considering economic, environmental, and technical resources. The procedures used in estimating incomes within the main categories of households/farms in the Carpathian mountainous areas of Romania, as well as the interpreted data in this study, are detailed in the Tables 1, 2, and 3.

Starting from the definition of the concept of efficiency, as a broad range of potential interpretations in resource utilization by Jollands (2006), we can analyze the farm through the lens of economic efficiency, simultaneously incorporating it into the concept of economic technical efficiency introduced by Farrell (1957).

To calculate the economic efficiency of farms in the mountainous region, various production parameters have been taken into account, such as animal weight, milk production, calving interval, restructuring, and productive lifespan.

For calculating expenses, the following aspects need to be taken into consideration: the quantity of milk consumed by the calf until weaning, the amount of concentrate required for cows and calves, fees for grazing and various associations to which farmers are enrolled, costs related to sanitary-veterinary services, etc.

Upon analyzing these calculations, it is observed that the efficiency of a farm increases with the growth in the number of animals. For a steady and substantial income, farmers often resort to enrolling their farms in the national animal improvement program and subjecting them to official milk production control. In this context, it's worth noting that a herd of 10 lactating cows can yield a profit of nearly 8000 euros per year. It is important to emphasize that this income is achievable only if the farmer produces the fodder on their own farm and does not incur expenses for hiring employees to care for the animals. Small farmers who raise two cows in contrast to those who have the conditions for raising and exploiting A6 or 10 dairy cows, incomes increase proportionally to the number of exploited animals.

Table 1. Estimation of the profitability of the work carried out on a farm that owns 2 milk cows, in the mountain area

Description	Value	UM
Parameters		
Weight of the cow	480	kg
Amount of milk during normal lactation	3200	kg
Calving Interval	365	zile
Exploitation period	10	ani
Reform percentage	10	%
INCOME		
Income for 1 kg of milk:		
• Summer	1.2	Lei
• Winter	1.4	Lei
Income from the milk of 2 cows:		
• Summer: 2 cows × 12 liters × (220 - 60) × 1.2 Lei	4608	Lei
• Winter: 2 cows × 8 liters × 145 days × 1.4 Lei	3248	Lei
Income from Meat:		
• Calves: 2 heads × 1000 Lei/head	3000	Lei
• Reformed Cows: 10% × 480 kg/cow × 8 Lei/kg × 2 cows	768	Lei
Total income from production/ year	11624	Lei
A.N.T./AN: 2 cows x 400 lei = 800 lei	800	Lei
Plant sector support : 2 ha x 1000 lei=2000 lei	2000	Lei
Total INCOME	14424	LEI
EXPENSES		
Milk for calves =400kg × 1,2lei/kg × 2 calves	960	Lei
Concentrates for calves = 25 kg/calf x 2.50 Lei/kg x 2 calves	125	Lei
Concentrates for cows = 1000 kg/cow x 1.5 Lei/kg x 2 cows	3000	Lei
Grazing fees = 600 Lei/cow x 2 cows	1200	Lei
Hay made in the household = 2200 kg/cow x 0.8 lei/kg x 2 heads	3250	Lei
Sanitary and veterinary actions = 250 x 2 cows	500	Lei
Water and electricity	700	Lei
Subscription	250	Lei
Other expenses	200	lei
Total EXPENSES	9935	Lei
ADVANTAGE = 14424 - 9935 = 4489 lei	4489	Lei
(1Euro = 4.9 Lei)	916.12	Euro
This income did not take into account the farmer's work.		
Income/month = 916.12 / 12	76.34	Euro

Table 2. Estimating the profitability of work carried out on a farm that owns 6 milk cows, in the mountain area

Description	Value	UM
Parameters		kg
Weight of the cow	480	kg
Amount of milk during normal lactation	3200	kg
Calving Interval	365	zile
Exploitation period	10	ani
Reform percentage	10	%
INCOME		
Income for 1 kg of milk:		
• Summer	1.2	Lei
• Winter	1.4	Lei
Income from the milk of 6 cows:		
• Summer: 6 cows × 12 liters × (220 - 60) × 1.2 Lei	13824	Lei
• Winter: 6 cows × 10 liters × 145 days × 1.4 Lei	13050	Lei
Income from Meat:		
• Calves: 6 heads × 1500 lei/head	9000	Lei
• Reformed cows: 10% × 450 × 8 lei/kg × 6 head	2160	Lei
Total income from production/ year:	38034	Lei
A.N.T.+ S.C.Z. only to those who are registered in C.O.P.L 2000 lei x 6 heads =	12000	
Plant sector support 6 ha x 1000 lei	6000	
Total INCOME	56034	lei
EXPENSES		
Milk for calves = 400 kg × 1,2 lei/kg × 6 calves	2880	Lei
Concentrates for calves = 25 kg/ calf × 2,5 Lei/kg × 6 calves	375	Lei
Concentrates for cows = 1000 kg/cow x 1.5 Lei/kg x 6 cows	9000	Lei
Grazing fees = 600 Lei/cow x 6 cows	3600	Lei
Hay made in the household = 2200kg/cow x 0.8lei/kg x 6 heads	10560	Lei
Sanitary and veterinary actions = 250 x 6 cows	1500	Lei
Water and electricity	1000	Lei
Subscription	1200	Lei
Other expenses	500	Lei
Total EXPENSES	30615	Lei
ADVANTAGE = 56034 - 30615 = 25419	25419	Lei
(1Euro = 4.9Lei)	5187.55	Euro
This income did not take into account the farmer's work.		
Income/month = 5187.55 / 12	432.29	Euro

Table 3. Estimating the profitability of work carried out on a farm that owns 10 milk cows, in the mountain area

Description	Value	UM
Parameters		
Weight of the cow	480	Kg
Amount of milk during normal lactation	3200	Kg
Calving Interval	365	Zile
Exploitation period	10	Ani
Reform percentage	10	%
INCOME		
Income for 1 kg of milk:		
• Summer	1.2	Lei
• Winter	1.4	Lei
Income from the milk of 10 cows:		
• Summer: 10 cows × 12 liters × (220 - 60) × 1.2 Lei	23040	Lei
• Winter: 10 cows × 10liters × 145 days × 1.4 Lei	20300	Lei
Income from Meat:		
• Calves: 10 heads × 1500 lei/head	15000	Lei
• Reformed Cows: 10% × 450 × 8 lei/kg × 10 head	3600	Lei
Total income from production/ year	61940	Lei
A.N.T.+ S.C.Z. only to those who are registered in C.O.P.L 2000 lei x 10 heads =	20000	Lei
Plant sector support 10 ha x 1000 lei	10000	Lei
Total INCOME	91940	Lei
EXPENSES		
Milk for calves =400 kg × 1,2 lei/kg × 10 calves	4800	Lei
Concentrates for calves = 25 kg/calf × 2,5 Lei/kg × 10 calves	625	Lei
Concentrates for cows = 1000 kg/cow x 1.5 Lei/kg x 10 cows	15000	Lei
Grazing fees = 600 Lei/cow x 10 cows	6000	Lei
Hay made in the household = 2200 kg/cow x 0.8 lei/kg x 10 heads	17600	Lei
Sanitary and veterinary actions = 250 x 10 cows	2500	Lei
Water and electricity	2500	Lei
Subscription	2000	Lei
Other expenses	500	Lei
Total EXPENSES	38025	Lei
ADVANTAGE = 91940 - 38025 = 53915	53915	Lei
(1Euro = 4.9Lei)	11003	Euro
This income did not take into account the farmer's work.		
Income/month = 11003 / 12	916,91	Euro

CONCLUSIONS

The contribution of this study can be summarized in the assessment of the conditions that shape the potential necessary for generating benefits and value from animal herds, integrating them into the context of heritage and cultural identity. Simultaneously, contributions are made to the analysis of the potential commercialization of local and regional agricultural products obtained from native breeds, as well as their use in promoting regional agrotourism. The study also argues for the underutilization of the potential for animal husbandry in the Carpathian mountain areas, confirming the significant impact of raising indigenous cattle breeds on the development of the agricultural sector in mountainous regions as invaluable cultural and civilizational assets. However, research in this area in mountain areas is limited due to the fact that mountain farmers have not yet adapted to the formation of associations or cooperatives, through which they would have a much higher potential in terms of benefits through the valorization of products and their commercialization.

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